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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****RETINOID EXPRESSION IN ONCHOCERCAL SKIN DISEASE:
PILOT STUDY****¹Dr. Muhammad Bilal Ahmed, ²Dr. Zeeshan Mahmood, ³Dr. Umaira Maqsood**¹MO, BHU Thatha Manik, Nowshera Virkan, Gujranwala.²MO, RHC Baddomalhi, Narowal.³WMO, RHC Kalaswala, Pasrur, Sialkot.**Abstract:**

This study is based on the reflection which the Onchocerca parasite volvulus selectively vitamin A absorption from the host, with recognized vitamin A toxicity in developed absorption, it was conjectured which mf (microfilariae) emancipate their vitamin A stores (retinoid) into host transmission in concentration of toxicity, persuading the symptoms and signs of onchocerciasis.

This study is planned as a pilot study to test the theory in Songa Communities, based on the data extracted from the PubMed website. According to collected data drug management with ivermectin may not execute by the survey time. The particular objective was to analyse the correlation between onchocerciasis diagnosis and high degrees of infection and retinoic acid sites.

The assessment was executing copy numbers of O volvulus of a genome current in skin snip specimens of onchocerciasis holding persons and correlating the numbers with levels of expression of receptor- α (RAR- α), retinoic acid, that is basically inducible by specific retinoic acid. Overall RNA and DNA were obtained from every 25 mf-negative and 25 mf-positive skin specimens and analyzing using polymerase quantitative chain reaction with suitable negative controls.

Sample's analysis, adjusted with the level of glyceraldehyde three phosphate dehydrogenase genes, exposed that many specimens with RAR- α transcript detectable had developed degrees of RAR- α manifestation than the control of assay. Furthermore, the number of samples and quality were inadequate for the analysis of statistics. Folded data on the level of presentation of both RAR RNA and O volvulus DNA advised a possible trend regarding higher relative RAR- α expression in the specimen with O volvulus DNA level (

Fold data on the expression levels of both O volvulus DNA and RAR RNA suggested a possible trend toward higher relative RAR- α expression in samples with higher levels of O ($r^2=0.25$, $P=.079$). Similarly, the contribution of vitamin A evidence to the pathology of onchocerciasis, therefore, relics elusive.

Keywords: *Onchocerciasis, skin, eye, retinoids, hypervitaminosis A, pathophysiology*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION:

“Onchocerciasis is basically an insidious and chronic disease which may transfer by “*Simulium sp.*” (Black flies). According to estimation 37 million, global people are infested with *Ochocera* parasite volvulus and almost 270000 are blind. The filarial nematode adult may endure for a decade in affected patients in subcutaneous nodules, discharging hundreds of thousands mf (microfilariae) that further trigger devastating visual impairment and itching. The disease origins enduring suffering and also catastrophic problems of socioeconomic in suffered communities (Baum et al., 2014).

The disease' epidemiology has altered in present years according to the local environment and also due to global changes in human population and climate with the core reason of parasite heterogeneity and dynamics in the response of the human host. According to the data, the disease has strongly caused for all villages abandoned where forty to fifty percent of adults are symptomatic. The efficiency of the main treatment “ivermectin” also declining; with highly alarming resistance indication of the drug. There is highly urgent requirement occurs, however, to comprehend the disease pathogenesis and to establish new strategies of treatment. Both ocular and dermatological, which considered major symptoms of the disease are linked with inflammatory reaction localization to dying mf and bacterial products circulated into the flow; therefore, the specific mechanisms of this specific disease are indeterminate (Brieger et al., 2015).

A probable understanding clue about the pathogenesis is that *O. volvulus* worms' adult selectively engrosses the overall vitamin A from the host, reasoning the retinoid of parasite concentrations to be significantly greater than those of encircling host tissues. We tried to extract the data from PubMed to show onchocerciasis four batches of adult worms regarding four multiple individuals and according to that data the concentration of median tissue retinol was 3.8µg/g (with the range of 0.5-11.9 µg/g) and 12.6 IU/g (with the range of 1.6-3.97 IU/g) that is eight times greater on basic values that according to the host skin, but inferior than in fresh liver (which is ~240µg/g. Skin biopsies and blood samples from all eight patients with onchocerciasis and also four uninfected clinically

controls demonstrated that retinol means plasma concentration in those patients was 40µg/100mL (with the range of 20-60µg/per 100 milliliters) (1.4IU/ per milliliters with the range of 0.8-1.9 (Mawson et al., 2017).

2.0 METHODS:

2.1 Study Area

This study was based on the PubMed database extracted from the largest database regarding onchocerciasis focused area in Tanzania. There were three further study sites named: Songea, Mbinga, and Namtumbo.

2.2 Study Design and Sampling Procedure

According to the PubMed database, the research started through community surveys which are designed to analyze OSD (onchocercal skin disease) with different individuals. Total numbers of adult's men and women were 106 with the age limit of 18-65 (there were 53 controls and 53 cases) which were originally recognized and requested for participate in the study. Probable presenting cases with OSDs with the presence of chronic and acute “popular onchodermatites” CPOD, depigmentation DSM, atrophy, and nodules which are diagnosed by an experienced physician in the clinical treatment of OSD. The confirmation happened through skin snips microscopy for mf (Mawson et al., 2017).

2.2.1 Specimen collection and processing

Samples were taken from left and right pelvic girdles, iliac crests, and buttocks gathered in the plates of 96 well microtiter 200µL with normal saline of 0.9% with the seal of para-film. All samples shipped frozen for processing to ACGT Incorporation, USA.

2.2.2 Assay Design

The copy number of *O. volvulus* genome assay was established by entering recognized *O. volvulus* genomic classifications into an appropriate bio-system based in Foster City, CA, USA. Multiple primer combinations were analyzed for non-*O. volvulus* recognition either nematodes or human other than *O. volvulus*, by successive primer sequences against the accessible National Centre's genomes for Biotechnology Information Site. The selected assay of *O. volvulus* had the minimum homology regarding non-*O. volvulus* sequence.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the study participants recruited in Ruvuma.

VARIABLE	CASES (N=53)	CONTROL (N=53)	P VALUE
Sex			
Male	37 (69.8)	26 (49.1)	.03
Female	16 (30.2)	27 (50.9)	
Age, y, mean (SD)	50.8 (12.5)	45.0 (14.3)	.02
Education			
None	20 (37.7)	14 (26.4)	.02
Primary	32 (60.4)	31 (58.5)	
Secondary	1 (1.9)	8 (15.1)	
Body mass index			
Mean (SD)	21 (2.8)	24.8 (4.4)	<.001
Occupation, No. (%)			
Peasants	51 (96.0)	45 (84.9)	
Clinical SS, No. (%)			
APOD	19 (35.9)	0 (0)	
CPOD	26 (49.1)	0 (0)	
DPM	16 (30.2)	0 (0)	
ATP	18 (34.0)	0 (0)	
Itching	49 (92.4)	0 (0)	

Abbreviations: APOD, acute papular onychodermatitis; ATP, atrophy; CPOD, chronic papular onychodermatitis; DPM, depigmentation; SD, standard deviation; SS, symptoms and signs.

(Source: Mawson et al., 2017)

2.2.3 DNA/RNA Abstraction and Harmonizing DNA Synthesis

All selected snips specimen were mixed with lysis buffer mixture and blizzards strongly for five minutes. RNA and DNA were then personally extricated while using the Nano-Drop Spectroscopy, UV/Vis spectrophotometer of Nano-Drop ND-8000 and Bio-analyzer 2100 (using Agilent Technologies Germany) (Mawson et al., 2017).

2.2.4 Qualitative data analysis and polymerase chain reaction

TaqMan, a target-specific assay regarding the sequence of *O. volvulus* genomic, for RAR- α transcript and specifically for the GAPDH “glyceraldehyde 3 phosphate dehydrogenase” genomic sequence was received from ABI “Applied Bio-systems Incorporation”. While using copy numbers assay, optimized assay conditions basically managed to give human genomic DNA samples from the blood. For each genomic DNA test sample both PCR targets basically intensified in triplicate using a system “HT7900 Sequence Detection System” by ABI (Okoye and Onwuliri, 2015).

(Source: Mawson et al., 2017)

3.0 RESULTS:

A patterned TaqMan (TaqMan probes basically hydrolysis probes which are established and designed to boost the PCR's quantitative specificity) assay regarding *O. volvulus* genomic DNA detection (Ovol2 detection) was established and blended at ABI (Applied Bio-systems Incorporation). Furthermore, the extra TaqMan regarding recognition of *RAR- α* expression about the human RNA and DNA normalizing levels were also gained as AOD (Assay-on-Demand) from ABI. Total RNA and genomic DNA were isolated from the snip samples of skin with extraction kit of Fisher SurePrep DNA/RNA (Mawson et al., 2017).

Specifically not linked with this study but one house blood sample was separately processed with the kit to gain negative control RNA and gDNA of a human. Quantity and quality of DNA improved from specimens and assessed with Nano-Drop spectroscopy. Though the outputs dissimilar promptly, all specimens were proposed for qPCR ("Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction") assessment. Accordingly, a sample of RNA was assessed with NanoDrop Spectroscopy, we seem most represented to have enough RNA quantity for testing (Ivove, 2016).

The set of eight samples of RNA was assessed with RNA Bio-analyzer regarding integrity and quality.

Though there was a good quality of RNA in assay control which is extracted from gathered blood samples, with the RIN “RNA Integrity Index” value of 9.6 the samples of RNA from the snips of skins have greatly tarnished RNA with low RNA integrity index (Ozoh et al., 2011).

Therefore, samples of all RNA were utilized to generate cDNA with the kit “SuperScript III” while utilizing 7.5 ng/RB=NA reaction, found by NanoDrop Reading. Accordingly, the DNA Genomic samples were assessed with an Ov2 assay for the appearance of genomes of *O. volvulus*. The related copy numbers of parasites were normalized to human genomic DNA copy number as mentioned by GAPDH assay and stated as SEM± fold averages related to the observed levels of negative AC (assay control). All those average CT values which gained for GAPDH assay represented that human DNA total amount which mentioned was similar in many specimens with some typically low DNA related exception regarding quality or quantity. *O. volvulus* DNA detected amounts, specifically, in the specimens vacillated from being untraceable in eleven of the specimen to higher than 1000 fold the contextual realized through assay control. Therefore, there was no obvious mf-positive and mf-negative correlation in groups and traced *O. volvulus* DNA levels (TÖRMÄ et al., 2016).

4.0 DISCUSSION:

According to this study, the purpose of representation was taking the first step to examine the retinoid toxicity theory in OSD patients. On this theory, the core symptoms regarding impaired vision and itch are caused by the prolonged recurrent revelation of eyes and skin to retinoid discharged into the tissues ensuring the large number deaths of mf on an everyday basis. There are multiple lines of evidence back the toxicity of retinoid theory of onchocerciasis (WENDLING, 2015).

O. volvulus generates antigens with greater affinity protein binding regarding retinol and fatty acid; accordingly, the Ov2 bindings of protein retinol and is copious to the wall of body specifically in the growing larvae. The Ov2 which is also known as OV-FAR-1 accumulates to greater levels in onchocercal nodules which are further concealed in vivo. RNA binding protein’s comparative amounts also found higher than avian origins and mammalian. Practical FAR may also be concealed by hookworms as to Ov-FAR-1 from *O. volvulus*, advising that FAR

secreted protein by nematodes parasites are critical to parasitism, probably having functions in motioning obtaining sterols from the hosts (Okoye and Onwuliri, 2015).

Initially, it has been advised that RBP contributor’s parasite release to eye and skin pathology by challenging for the interfering and ligand with the transport mechanisms of host’s retinol which is localized state of deficiency of vitamin D creation (Ozoh et al., 2011).

Secondly, the features of the common clinic of onchocerciasis that is a musculoskeletal pain, pruritus, lethargy, bone changes and development seizure in children are accordingly reported succeeding undue vitamin A intakes after continued treatment with a retinoid. Qualities of onchocerciasis are multiple visual deficiencies and DSM of skin (Mawson et al., 2017).

Third, the theory could justify in therapeutic efficacy as part of the largely utilized anti-filarial medication ivermectin. Though ivermectin is recognized to intermingle with postsynaptic GluCl1 “Glutamate-gated Chloride Channels”, resultant in mf paralysis the effectiveness of therapeutic ivermectin vestiges partially understood only (Mawson et al., 2017).

Coherent with this theory, ivermectin contends proficiently with retinol for “retinol-binding” established on parasite RBP and has a greater similarity of parasite RBP as compared with retinol. There is a correlation also presents between the ivermectin analogues and binding affinities with their anti-parasitic action. Accordingly, the action of therapeutic ivermectin may consequently with parasite vitamin A uptake (Brieger et al., 2015).

5.0 CONCLUSION:

A PCR TaqMan real-time assay was vigorously established regarding *O. volvulus* DNA genomic levels in specimens of a human. Though the demonstrated assay has a low context in human DNA control specimen, it required an *O. volvulus* DNA targeted validated positive control to enumerate its implementation. As genuine *O. volvulus* genomic DNA endures inaccessible, there is a recommendation available to synthesize the target region assay in a plasmid, to be utilized as regularized control of copy number. RNA and DNA both were extricated from the snip samples of skin. Therefore, the RNA quality was promptly despoiled

which affected negatively the interpretation and validity of outputs. The RNA use preservation components like RNA later is largely recommended in any futuristic study for gathering, formulating and storing RNA tissue sample assessment. No palpable correlation between sample assignment and O volvulus DNA levels to mf positive or negative groups were demonstrated but there is a possible inclination advising increasing RAR levels of expression with high levels of O volvulus DNA noted. Therefore, it is highly recommended for further studies, specifically to confirm this correlation validity.

REFERENCES:

1. Appa, Y. (2014). Retinoid Therapy: Compatible Skin Care. *Skin Pharmacology and Physiology*, 12(3), pp.111-119.
2. Baum, S., Greenberger, S., Pavlotsky, F., Solomon, M., Enk, C., Schwartz, E. and Barzilai, A. (2014). Late-onset onchocercal skin disease among Ethiopian immigrants. *British Journal of Dermatology*, 171(5), pp.1078-1083.
3. Brieger, W., Ososanya, O., Kale, O., Oshiname, F. and Oke, G. (2015). Gender and ethnic differences in onchocercal skin disease in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, 2(6), pp.529-534.
4. Eneanya, C. and Nwaorgu, O. (2006). Social and psychological aspects of onchocercal skin disease in Nkwelle-Ezunaka, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*, 22(1).
5. Ivoke, N. (2016). An Epidemio-Dermatological Assessment Of Onchocercal Skin Diseases In Awum, Enugu State, Nigeria. *Bio-Research*, 2(2).
6. Lever, N. (2006). Ivermectin reduces morbidity associated with onchocercal skin disease. *Inpharma Weekly*, &NA;(791), pp.12-13.
7. Mawson, A., Makunde, W., Penman, A., Hernandez Morales, V., Kalinga, A., Francis, F., Rubinchik, S. and Kibweja, A. (2017). Retinoid Expression in Onchocercal Skin Disease: Pilot Study. *Infectious Diseases: Research and Treatment*, 10, p.117863361773174.
8. Okoye, I. and Onwuliri, C. (2015). Epidemiology and psycho-social aspects of onchocercal skin diseases in northeastern Nigeria. *Filaria Journal*, 6(1), p.15.
9. Ozoh, G., Murdoch, M., Bissek, A., Hagan, M., Ogbuagu, K., Shamad, M., Braide, E., Boussinesq, M., Noma, M., Murdoch, I., Sékétéli, A. and Amazigo, U. (2011). Onchocerciasis Control: impact on onchocercal skin disease. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, 16(7), pp.875-883.
10. TÖRMÄ, H., LÖNTZ, W., LIU, W., ROLLMAN, O. and VAHLQUIST, A. (2016). Expression of cytosolic retinoid-binding protein genes in human skin biopsies and cultured keratinocytes and fibroblasts. *British Journal of Dermatology*, 131(2), pp.243-249.
11. WENDLING, P. (2015). Retinoid-Hyaluronate Connection Evaluated. *Skin & Allergy News*, 36(11), p.23.